

IMPLEMENTATION OF AUTOMATIC DRAINAGE CLEANING SYSTEM USING SOLAR PANEL

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ABSTRACT

All forms of life on Earth need water as a fundamental requirement. There may be 70% water on Earth, but most of it is unfit for human consumption. Because of its many uses, including drinking, bathing, cleaning, cooking, etc., clean water is in high demand. The primary role of the automated drainage system is to gather and dispose of solid waste by means of forks into the waste tray. Discarded items such as paper, plastic bags, and empty bottles make up the solid waste in drainage water. A clog in the drainage system could be the result of dirty water. So as to sidestep

circumstances, these contaminants must be periodically removed to ensure the uninterrupted flow of drainage water. The model's driving mechanism allows for continual cleaning of the drain, which involves removing solid waste and depositing it into a collecting tray. Starting the system's efficient operation is the primary goal of this project's design. At the first sign of an obstruction, this project's chain sprocket-driven prongs scoop up solid debris and deposit it into the garbage bucket, automatically cleaning the water in the drainage system. As an added bonus, it lessens the danger to humans and the expense of physical labour.

INTRODUCTION:

A drain cleaner machine is a device that replaces human labour in the physical removal of waste from an open canal, river, or drainage tunnel. By reducing the need for people to physically handle rubbish, we can help stop the spread of illness. The pillars supporting bridges in rivers and canals often get clogged with plastic and other forms of trash, which prevents water from flowing freely.

On the way to the recycling facility, they may be conveyed. A drain cleaner is a consumer product that is formulated with chemicals to either unclog sewer pipes or aid in their prevention from becoming clogged. The term might also describe the person who uses plumber's snakes or chemical drain cleaners to accomplish the task. There are two main types of drain cleaners: chemical and device. The first line of defence against soft blockages like hair and grease that may build up near interior drain openings is a drain cleaner, which is often the first line of defence against clogged drains in a single sink, toilet, tub or shower. For this purpose, you may use drain cleaners such as plungers, chemical drain cleaners, hand-held drain augers, air burst drain cleaners, and home remedy drain cleaners. When more than one plumbing fixture becomes clogged, the next step is to use a drain cleaner. This tool may remove both soft and hard obstacles from the drain opening all the way to the main sewer drain and the outside pipework. Sewer jettors and electric drain cleaners are designed for this exact purpose. This is

often used to remove mechanical impurities from sewage water. Every living thing, including humans, need water to sustain life.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Waste Management in India: An Overview An inevitable consequence of development and industrial progress is generation of waste. Therefore, efficient waste management is a matter of international concern and countries have set up robust regulatory waste management regimes for balancing the objectives of development and environments sustainability. In India, the National Environment Policy, 2006 while suggesting measures for controlling various forms of environmental pollution lay emphasis on the need for collection and treatment systems for recycling wastes and devising measures for environmentally safe disposal of residues.¹ In India, waste management is governed by various subordinate legislations and the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of India ("MoEF") in conjunction with State Pollution Control Boards of different states ("SPCB") administer the gamut of waste management regulations. This bulletin aims at providing an overview of the various rules governing waste management in India and the issues faced in their compliance.

A. From our literature surveys, it was found that the drainage system's actually does not have any standard dimensions; that is the width and the depth of the drains are varied according to the parallel road networks, eg: the size of a drain in the urban areas will be much more larger than the drains in the rural areas. To meet these requirements we choose to include a retractable and extensible feature to our prototype. The use of a screw nut arrangement to adjust the mechanism's breadth and height accomplishes this. Near the mechanism, you'll see the solar panel

and batteries installed on a pole or post. Mechanical designs may replace the traditional method of drain cleaning, as shown by B. Ganesh UL and Vinod Rampur¹. There is a danger to human life and the fact that drain pipes are unsanitary to clean. A mechanical system, including a semi-automatic drainage cleaner, was used to address this issue by regularly removing the waste. By using this method of drain cleaning, several environmental concerns might be decreased. A.H. Ingle², Milind Kolhe, Rahul Shende, and R.C. Waghule collaborated on the development of an automated system that might lessen the need for human labour. The workers would have an easier time clearing the drains of debris if this was in place. The crew is relieved since they were able to clean it without having to access the drainage systems. It was useful in preventing harm to humans and the environment.

The 2005 Mumbai floods were brought to light by C. Manoj Rathod, Vasant Pund, Rahul Pangale, and Jivan Rathod. The flood killed almost 2,000 people. The accumulation of non-biodegradable trash, such as plastic bags, bottles, and thermocol, clogged the drain lines, leading to the flooding. The flood issue gets quite serious as a result of all this garbage. They were successful in cleaning up the wastewater using their drainage system design.

expedites the process and reduces the amount of time needed to clean the drain pipes.

The drainage cleaning system was completely automated with the help of the PLC SCADA system, which D. Balchandra G., Karthikeyan S., Elongovan K., and Divyn N.⁴ installed. The system also

included a pump monitoring system, control system with a gas exhauster, pressure valve, stepper motor, and level sensor. The equipment detects when water and gas are flowing through it and adjusts the engine speed accordingly. To make the machine even more eco-friendly, E. Murgank Sharma, Shahabaz Siddique, Archit, Pawan Shrivastava, and Shivam Kumar Tiwari⁵ went the extra mile. Though it ran on energy from solar panels, the newly-designed mechanical cleaner was unautomated and had a set chain speed. The mechanism that regulates the motor's speed was nonexistent. Consideration of an electronic bucket was proposed by F. R. Sathiakala, S. Flora Grace, P. Maheshwari, S. MajithaBhanu, and R. Muthulakshmi⁶. The bin is often used for disposing of rubbish that has been gathered from the collector. The garbage will be thrown into the bin. These materials will be in a moist state. Because many illnesses thrive in moist environments, this might wreak much more harm. Not to mention that an unhealthy atmosphere is the result of moist garbage, which stinks much worse. Mechanical and human labour systems were contrasted by G. Dr. Kumaresan, ME, PhD. His primary considerations in drawing this comparison were economy, efficiency, and time. How much time

lower and more cost-effective as a result of the system. Working by hand is more taxing on the body and takes more time. The mechanical system was more efficient than the human. According to H.S.D. Anap, one of the main causes of pollution in urban areas is the frequent flooding of drainage systems. His invention aided in the detection of the

clog in the drainage systems. The drainage pipes' condition may be more accurately monitored with the aid of the system. Providing up-to-the-minute information on the circumstances was also helpful. The state of the drainage pipes was better monitored thanks to the installation of a wireless sensor network. We utilised a level sensor to keep an eye on how much water was flowing through the drain pipes. I. M. Raveena Reddy used mathematical model analysis to design a system for generating gears with shifted profiles. The teeth undercutting of an unconventional elliptical gear was examined using the mathematical model that was suggested. This was useful in creating driven and driving gears.

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION:

1. Lane Changes
2. Gentle Curves
3. Junctions
4. Chain drive movements
5. U-Turns
6. Not applicable in Commercial/Industrial outlets
7. Not applicable in Domestic junction outlets
8. Efficiency is low
9. Not suitable at the time of heavy flows.

RESEARCH SCOPE:

The main objective of this project is to minimize or overcome the problem which can be faced in manual machine. Also increased the dumping rate of waste. And help the operator to do easily work.

The purpose of selecting drain wastewater cleaner machine are as follows-

1. Simplicity of Design and Control.
2. This type of machine is easy to operate and less time consuming.
3. Evaluate the effectiveness of alternative

ainagedesignandoperational practices, to reduce nitrate-N losses from drained agricultural lands

4. Assess the impact of various soil and crop management practices on reducing nitrate-

N loading to subsurface drains.

5. Assess the need for further research in other aspects of water quality from drained agricultural lands, including the emerging issues of pathogens and phosphorus from manure applications.

6. Develop drainage guides and other extension materials, and work with state and federal action agencies, to assist in implementation of improved design and management practices for subsurface drainage systems.

Keeping in mind the natural calamities and Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan we have made this project.

CONCLUSION:

Manufacturing processes may be operated and controlled via the use of automation technology, which involves mechanical, electrical, and computer-based systems. One of our sewage cleaning systems uses this technique. In addition, we are in possession of

We adhered to the study of motion and time and used the resources at our disposal to create a project that was both inexpensive and efficient. Using solar energy improves the system's efficiency. We were able to effectively develop, build, and test this system. It does the job well. Using the principles of gear shifting and shaft coupling, the drain waste water cleaner machine is developed and made. Shafts, a DC geared motor, a dust bin, bearings, sprockets, and chains make up the majority of it. There is no shortage of readily accessible and easy-to-assemble fabrication materials.

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